

Assessing Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Pharmacovigilance and Adverse Drug Reaction Reporting Among Undergraduate Medical Students: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Pharmacovigilance means detecting, assessing, and preventing adverse drug reactions (ADRs). This study examines the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of medical undergraduates towards pharmacovigilance and ADR.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey evaluated 300 under graduate medical students at Government Medical College, Suryapet, focusing on demographics and KAP. Data interpretation employed descriptive statistics.

Demographics: Participants were primarily aged 18-20 (62.3%) and 21-23 (37.7%), with a gender distribution of 48.3% males and 51.7% females. Most were in their 2nd or 3rd year (72.7%).

Knowledge: A significant 81.7% correctly identified ADRs. Pharmacovigilance's role in post marketing surveillance was understood by 76.3%. Awareness of the National Centre for ADR Monitoring in Ghaziabad was at 71.8%. Most (95%) acknowledged the fatality risk in severe ADRs and healthcare professionals' reporting role (92%).

Attitudes: A strong inclination for mandatory ADR reporting (69.7%) and its positive impact on patient safety (86%) was evident. High percentages (95.3% and 91%) viewed ADR reporting as a professional obligation and an area where medical students can contribute.

Practices: Difficulties in ADR reporting were encountered by 41.3%, mostly due to the unavailability of forms (35.7%) and time constraints (27%). Awareness of immediate cessation for severe ADRs was high (78.7%), and 66.3% had reported ADRs. Preferred reporting methods were via email or website (44.7%), with 42.3% prioritizing patient management over reporting.

Conclusion: The study revealed diverse degrees of knowledge, attitude, and practice in undergraduate medical students concerning pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting. Favourable views towards ADR reporting were noted. Tackling obstacles and improving education are crucial for equipping future healthcare workers to contribute meaningfully to patient safety.

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Introduction

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs), as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), encompass any unintended, harmful response resulting from drug use at therapeutic doses for diagnosis, prevention, or treatment of a disease, or even for physiological purposes [1].

Ensuring the safety and efficacy of drugs is paramount in the realm of medical practice, making pharmacovigilance a vital discipline for safeguarding patient well-being on a global scale. The WHO characterizes pharmacovigilance (PV) as "the process of detecting, evaluating, and comprehending adverse events or any other drug-related issues [1]."

Thus, the timely reporting of ADRs stands as the cornerstone of any robust pharmacovigilance plan, especially when ADRs can lead to severe consequences such as hospitalization, disability, or even life-threatening situations [2].

Rationale of the study

In the realm of healthcare, it is primarily the responsibility of physicians to identify and report significant ADRs. Their likelihood of fulfilling this duty is significantly influenced by their confidence in detecting, managing, and preventing these adverse events. Unfortunately, numerous studies published in international ADR publications often

fail to yield conclusive results, primarily owing to deficiencies in the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to PV activities and ADR reporting [3].

It is significant to highlight that, despite the vital role of pharmacovigilance and ADR studies in healthcare, Suryapet has remained largely unexplored in this regard. Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of undergraduate medical students concerning pharmacovigilance and adverse drug reactions (ADRs).

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Duration: This study utilized a cross-sectional, semi-structured, and anonymous Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) survey conducted during the period from May 2023 to July 2023.

Sampling and Participants: A total of 300 undergraduate medical students enrolled at Government Medical College, Suryapet, were selected using purposive sampling techniques.

Data Collection: Data collection was primarily accomplished through a structured questionnaire, comprising four distinct sections:

Demographic Characteristics: This section collected information on age, gender, and the year of study.

Knowledge of ADR Reporting and Pharmacovigilance: This section included questions about the definition of ADRs and Pharmacovigilance, the location of the National Coordinating Center for ADR Monitoring, the outcomes of serious ADRs, who can report ADRs, types of ADRs documented, and awareness of the WHO online database for reporting ADRs.

Attitudes towards ADR Reporting and Pharmacovigilance: This section assessed whether ADR reporting was considered mandatory, whether it enhances patient safety, whether ADR reporting is seen as a professional obligation for all healthcare providers, the role of medical students in ADR reporting, and the perceived usefulness of having collection boxes at all clinical departments for facilitating proper reporting.

Practices of ADR Reporting and Pharmacovigilance: This section covered any difficulties encountered in reporting ADRs, specifics of these challenges, recommended actions in response to suspected drug-related serious ADRs, personal history of ADR reporting, reporting methods, and factors that might deter individuals from reporting ADRs.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical principles were rigorously followed throughout this study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection commenced.

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics served as the primary analytical approach in this research. These statistics enabled researchers to summarize and present the collected data in a clear and informative manner. The insights derived from this analysis will inform future investigations and policies pertaining to ADR reporting and awareness of pharmacovigilance.

Results

Demographic Characteristics: The majority of participants fell into two age groups: 18-20 years (comprising 62.3% of the sample) and 21-23 years (constituting 37.7%). The gender distribution was nearly equal, with 48.3% identifying as male and 51.7% as female. The largest proportion of participants (72.7%) were in their 2nd and 3rd years of study.

	Group	%
Age	18-20	62.3
	21-23	37.7
Gender	Male	48.3
	Female	51.7
Year of study	2 nd year	55.7%
	3 rd year	17%

Knowledge: In the assessment of knowledge, participants were presented with seven questions. Here are the key findings:

An impressive 81.7% of respondents correctly identified Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs). A substantial 76.3% demonstrated an understanding of the post-marketing role of pharmacovigilance.

Approximately 71.8% of participants were aware of the National ADR Monitoring Centre located in Ghaziabad. Notably, a vast majority (95%) acknowledged the potential risk of death associated with serious ADRs. The pivotal role of doctors in ADR management was emphasized by 92% of respondents (Table 1).

Table 1: Shows the student response to knowledge domain questions.

Students responses to knowledge related questions	
Questions	Frequency
1. What do you understand by term ADR's?	81.7%
2. What is Pharmacovigilance?	76.3%
3. Where is National Coordinating centre for ADR monitoring?	71.8%
4. What is outcome of serious ADR?	95%
5. Who can report ADR?	92%
6. Which type of ADR's should be documented?	87.5%

Attitude: In examining participants' attitudes, we explored five personality-based questions, yielding the following noteworthy insights: A significant 96% of respondents expressed a strong preference for mandatory Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) reporting. An overwhelming 94% believed that ADR reporting positively impacts patient safety. An impressive 92% and 92% of participants

viewed ADR reporting as not only a professional activity but also an area where medical students can actively contribute.

A substantial 92.2% considered the placement of collection boxes in all clinical departments as a helpful measure for facilitating proper ADR reporting (Table 2).

Table 2: Shows students' response to personality based questions

Students responses attitude domain questions	
Questions	Frequency
1. Do you think reporting ADR should mandatory?	96%
2. Do you think reporting ADR's will increase patient safety?	94%
3. Do you think ADR reporting is a part of professional obligation for all health care providers?	92%
4. Do you think medical students could play a role in ADR reporting?	92%
5. Do you think collecting boxes at all clinical departments is helpful for proper reporting?	92.2%

Figure 1:

Practice: When it comes to actual practice, participants were presented with seven questions to gauge their behaviors and experiences. Here are the key findings: A substantial portion, 41.3%, reported encountering problems in Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) reporting. The primary challenges cited included a lack of information (35.7%) and time constraints (27%). Impressively, 78.7% of respondents demonstrated a high level of awareness

regarding prompt decision-making for adverse reactions. A notable 66.3% of participants reported having experience in reporting adverse reactions.

The most preferred methods for ADR reporting were through email or websites, chosen by 44.7% of respondents. Interestingly, 42.3% of participants prioritized patient management over the reporting of ADRs (Table No:3).

Table 3: Shows students response towards practice domain.

Response of students to Practice based questions	
Questions	Frequency
1. Do you find any difficulties in reporting ADR's?	41.3%
2. If yes, what difficulties?	35.7%
3. Upon occurrence of serious ADR. What needs to be done with suspected drug?	78.7%
4. Have you reported an ADR?	66.3%
5. If yes; where?	66.3%
6. Which method would you prefer to send information to an ADR reporting centre?	44.7%
7. Which of the following factors that discourage you to reporting ADR's?	42.3%

Figure 2: Reasons for not reporting ADR's by medical students at Government medical college

Reasons for not reporting ADR's by medical students: In our research, the primary factors contributing to the under reporting of Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) encompass a variety of challenges. The foremost hindrance is a deficiency in ADR training and awareness, accounting for 49% of cases. Additionally, 47.5% of respondents cited their unfamiliarity with the procedures and channels for reporting ADRs as a significant barrier. A lack of access to ADR reporting forms was reported by 20.6% of participants, while 16.9% believed that prioritizing patient care management took precedence over ADR reporting. Other factors contributing to underreporting include difficulties in obtaining patient cooperation (16.2%), concerns regarding legal liabilities (15.5%), and time constraints (9.1%).

Discussion

Pharmacovigilance plays a pivotal role in the realm of healthcare, contributing significantly to the identification and prevention of adverse drug reactions (ADRs). Consistent and timely reporting of ADRs is a linchpin for the effectiveness of any

pharmacovigilance program. While numerous studies have assessed the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) of doctors in drug preparation, limited attention has been given to understanding the knowledge and practices of junior doctors in this domain⁴. Our study is among the few that delves into the KAP of pharmacovigilance among medical students.

Our institution, GMC, situated in Suryapet, Telangana, India, serves as an Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring Center (AMC) operating within the Department of Pharmacology. We receive reports of adverse reactions from various medical specialties, including Dermatology, Medicine, and Anesthesia. Notably, our study reveals that a significant proportion of students scored either average or low KAP scores. It is evident from our findings that approximately 80% of students possess knowledge about pharmacovigilance and ADRs, with 89% recognizing the mandatory nature of ADR reporting and its positive impact on patient safety. These figures align with a study conducted on

undergraduate medical students at a tertiary care teaching hospital in South India [5].

The overarching goal of pharmacovigilance is to safeguard patient well-being and promote the effective utilization of medications. The primary impediment to achieving this goal remains the dearth of knowledge and proficiency in drug preparation, as highlighted by our study and substantiated by prior research. Addressing this challenge necessitates educational interventions such as the integration of pharmacovigilance programs into postgraduate practices, fostering continuing professional development (CPD), and providing specialized pharmacovigilance training [11].

Indeed, the absence of Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR) reporting is a critical issue in healthcare, with some students prioritizing patient management over reporting ADRs. Patient confidentiality, doctor-patient communication, lack of patient cooperation, fear of legal liability, and time constraints are also significant factors contributing to underreporting. [6]

Addressing these reasons for underreporting necessitates the integration of ADR training courses into clinical practice. Ensuring that reporting containers are readily available at all clinics can facilitate proper reporting [7]. Moreover, fostering meaningful discussions on ADRs and providing guidance on how to fill out ADR reporting forms during medication-based therapy sessions can mitigate the factors that lead to underreporting of ADRs [8].

It is paramount to recognize that knowledge plays a pivotal role in shaping behavior and practice. As medical graduates are the future doctors of our healthcare system, comprehensive training in recognizing, reporting, and preventing ADRs should be an integral part of their education [9]. By equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge, we can significantly enhance pharmacovigilance efforts and promote patient safety in clinical practice [10].

Conclusion

The study has illuminated a spectrum of knowledge, attitudes, and practices among undergraduate medical students in relation to pharmacovigilance and the reporting of Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs). Encouragingly, the findings indicate a positive disposition towards ADR reporting among the students. It is evident that addressing the existing obstacles and enhancing educational initiatives are of paramount importance. By doing so, we can better prepare future healthcare professionals to make substantial contributions to patient safety. This underscores the need for a concerted effort to improve the

understanding, attitudes, and practices related to pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting among the upcoming generation of healthcare workers.

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